

Employee Assistance Program and Organisational Performance of Warmco Nigeria Plc, Lagos State

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Abstract:- This paper investigated the effect of employee assistance program on the organisational performance of Wamco Nigeria Plc. The study identified the existing employee assistance program and examined the effect of health care assistance program on organisational productivity. The population of the study was six hundred and fifty-two (652) employees of Wamco Nigeria Plc out of which two hundred (200) employees were derived as a sample size using Taro Yamane's formula. The study used primary sources of data; the instrument used was well structured questionnaire administered through Goggle form. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. E-view package was employed as a statistical tool in testing the research hypotheses at 5% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that health care assistance program, wellness assistance program, stress management, counselling program and mental health among others are the available programs in Wamco Nigeria Plc. The result of the study revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between health care assistance program and organisational performance. The study concluded that the employees' performance could be improved and sustained as a result of the available employee assistance programs and this will ultimately improve the overall organisational performance. The study therefore recommended that the management of Warmco Nigeria Plc should strengthen the available employee assistance programs and also try to know the assistance program that satisfies the need of each employee by not generalizing things.

Keywords:- Employee, Health care, Wellness, Counseling, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The employers and the employees of the various organisation could benefit from the available programs in respect of employees assistance that are established as a result of policy of the organisation. Personal concern that could affect the workers performance at one time or the other are taken serious by the business owners through the provision of Employee Assistance Programs (EAP) that could help the employees' but indirectly address the issues of productivity among the employees (Jegade & Bolaji, 2017). EAP enhances performance of an organization with employee productivity in mind. One of the tools that could

be used to indicate effectiveness of the workplace is by establishment and maintenance of EAP with tendency to improving workers' health and productivity, reducing the employees' turnover intention and reabsorbing effort made after illnesses or injuries (Crawford, 2017).

According to Bozeman, Perrew & Hochwarter, 2017; Mundle, 2017, the focus of the EAP include instruction on handling addicted workers, mental health issues and stress in the place of work. The physical and mental well-being of the workers is one of the activities of the human resource unit of any typical organisation while EAP make available short-term counseling directed to an individual, and expert assessment on issues that are related to work schedule which might cause disruptions to workers effectiveness and efficiency or their well-being (Zarkin, Bray & Qi, 2019). Availability of EAP help the workers to deal with unpalatable conditions that poses stress on the job and it likewise give the business owners an opportunity to get the best of the workers effort (Ajala & Osunrinde, 2020).

Recently, there are concerted effort by the management of various organizations to integrate service and resources to support not only the physical and mental health of the workers but also to include disease management, preventive health and other things that could facilitate work-life-balance (Shahbaz & Raza, 2017). To a large extent, there is business sense in ability of business owber to alleviate or eliminate some issues bordering an individual, family, and entire workers in the workplace through proactive and preventive measures that could avert the uncontrollable issues before it get out of hand (Atieno & Otsyulah, 2019). This study identify available employee assistance program for employees in Wamco Nigeria, Plc and also analyse the influence of health care assistance program on organisational efficiency and effectiveness of Wamco Nigeria, Plc. In addition to this, the following hypotheses are examined:

- H_{01} = Employee Assistance Program has no significant effect on Effectiveness and Efficiency of Wamco Nigeria Plc.
- H_{02} = Health Care Assistance Program does not have significant effect on Effectiveness and Efficiency of Wamco Nigeria Plc.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Assistance Program

The employee assistance program is an employee well-being program that provides service to employees feeling mental problems resulting from their work – family related issues (Jerrell & Dean, 2021). A major technique of occupational stress management that is made available is a psychological service to the employees. The program was developed to ensure that the overall performance of the workers are optimal and the hindrances like stress, depression, anxiety, drug addiction, marital problems, career issues, financial troubles and workplace conflict among others; they are often dealt with by the occupational stress management services (Salomon, Dickin, Gray, Grisso, Cummiskey, Krotki, & Pollack, 2010; Secapramana, Anggoro & Hariyanto, 2020) It provides EAP with a legal obligation to project the image of the organisation as a caring workplace that reduce occupational stress and thereby increase productivity (Huda, 2018).

According to Dannenfeldt, Stassen and Stauffer, (2017) the role of the employee assistance programs in enhancing employee well-being cannot be over-emphasized which will help them to improve and sustain their various activities within the workplace (Donnelly, Valentine, & Oehme, 2015). Assessment of the EAP performance should be done so as to know the implication of its development in the workplace, maintaining the imitative of improvement and effectiveness through regular monitoring and program evaluation. Counselors should be well-trained and hired under accredited professional development program so as to get the best from them. Additionally, counselors' adequate experience will help in a large extent to add value to the beneficiaries.

The basic things that the EAP needs to be a success include provision of employee well-being service that reduce if not total elimination of work-family related challenges Also, EAP counselor performance in terms of quality and significant commitment should be ensued. Lastly, the EAP should bridge the gap between the employees' productivity and job satisfaction (Pavicic & Kozina, 2017).

B. The Need for EAP

Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) play a crucial role in supporting the well-being of employees within organizations (Attridge, 2019 cited in Brun et al., 2003; Kahn & Langlieb, 2003), The programs address various needs, including mental health, work-related stress, personal challenges and more EAPs contribute to:

Comprehensive reviews of the research literature on workplace mental health abound, including reports by researchers business groups and consultants (Attridge, 2019 cited in American Psychiatric Association, 2006; National Business Group on Health/Finch & Phillips, 2005; Watson Wyatt Worldwide, 2007), the Canadian government (Attridge, 2019 cited in Larson et al., 2007), the United States government, the European Union (Attridge, 2019

cited in McDaid, 2008), and the World Health Organisation (Attridge, 2019 cited in WHO); There are a number of conclusions from these reviews that support the need for more employer attention to workplace mental health and addiction issues and thus also to the need for EAP services:

- Mental health support: EAPs offer confidential counseling services aiding employees dealing with stress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues, fostering a healthier workplace.
- Work-Life Balance: Supporting employees in managing personal and professional demands. EAPs help maintain a balance, reducing burnout, and improving overall job satisfaction.
- Crisis Intervention: EAPs provides immediate assistance during crises, such as accidents or traumatic events helping employees cope and enabling smoother recovery process.
- Increased Productivity: By addressing personal challenges, EAPs contribute to improve focus, reduces absenteeism, and increased productivity, benefitting both the employers and the employees
- Conflict Resolution: EAPs assist in resolving workplace conflicts, enhancing communication skills, and promoting a positive work environment, leading to better teamwork and collaboration.
- Financial Wellness: EAPs include financial counseling, helping employees manage their finances effectively, reducing financial stress and enhancing overall well-being
- Health and Wellness Programs: EAPs often offer wellness initiatives, promoting healthy lifestyles, which can lead to decreased healthcare costs for both employees and employers.
- Preventive Measures: By addressing issues at an early stage, EAPs help prevent significant problems from developing, contributing to a strong organisational culture.

C. Employees Assistance Program and Performance

The relationship between EAPs and performance is intertwined. By providing employees with the tools to manage personal challenges, EAPs can contribute to improved mental health, reduced stress and increased overall wellbeing. In turn, this can positively affect job satisfaction and productivity. Organizations often implement EAPs as part of a holistic approach to employee well-being recognizing the interconnectedness of personal and professional aspects of life. Effective EAPs can lead to a healthier, more engaged workforce, ultimately influencing performance and contributing to a positive workplace culture.

Aftermath effects of EAPs on the employee and the employer cannot be overemphasized n any organization, though the cost involved may be felt by the organization they still get the benefits that are higher than the cost spent. The EAPs have cushion the effect that the work-related problems have on the performance of the employees even the problem of absenteeism and presenteeism that could have brought challenges to the success of the business owners (Clark, Michel, Zhdanova, Pomeroy & Baltés,

2019). The behavioural science is used for the evaluation and execution of certain problems related to work and those that are not work related over a period of time; this has made the operation of EAPs to be on individual employee. The EAP needed by one individual may not be the same with other workers in the same organisation (Nunes, Richmond, Pampel & Wood, 2017). The behavioural science interventions on the individual employee level have significant outcome on the overall workplace performance (Rubinstein, 2018).

D. Theoretical review

➤ *Affect Theory*

Edwin Locke's propounded the Affect theory in 1976; it is arguably the most notable job fulfillment model. The foundation of this theory is that the fulfillment derived from the workplace and works itself are highly determined by the expectation and realization of an individual. The theory states that the level of values that an individual placed on the job is the extent of the fulfillment that he or she derives from the workplace and the works itself which may have a rub-off effect on the performance of an individual. For instance, somebody that attach high value to a particular job tends to get more satisfaction when expectations are met and the opposite is the case when the expectation are not met, they are somehow unfulfilled or dissatisfied if compared to somebody who do not put high value in that job. An employee may be satisfied because of provision of a particular EAP made available by the management. The essence of this theory is that employee has individual need or personal problem that may not be the same with other people in the same unit or department. The employer therefore has to interview an individual on what their needs look like and how the available programs will suit their needs and provide based on the awareness of such need rather than generalization of the EAPs that the management and HR deem fit. The situation can then be on what satisfied an individual rather than what satisfy the management (Atieno & Otsyulah, 2019).

Critics of affect theory argue that it attention on non-conscious bodily experiences and emotions can lead to a lack of clear methodology and variability making it challenging to establish rigorous empirical evidence. Other scholars question the conceptual ambiguity and fluidity of terms within affect theory, hindering a precise understanding of its concepts. This study will be anchored on this theory.

➤ *Spill-Over Theory*

This theory was propounded by Staines Spill in 1980 where work and family operate as one entity and they influence each other (Nkanata, 2021). It developed the circumstances by which spill over occurs between the work set up and the family set up which tends to be significant or insignificant. In case of rigidity in the structure if interaction between the work-family and the available time and space. Whereas, in a case where individual are enabled to integrate and overlap the work and family responsibilities in time and space leads to a flexibility in the workplace structure which metamorphose to healthy work-life balance. Work context

(the psychological and physical, workplace culture, nature of the interaction between the workers, demands of the job in term of social an emotion) and family context (upbringing, education, age and environment religion, values among others) are major determinant of work-life-balance. The work life balance nature when defined objectively it refers to as the hours that work needs to be done or that an individual perform a task, the available time that could be spend outside the workplace. Subjectively, work-life-balance refers to as the condition of being stable and instability. He also noted that there is stability when equal credence is given to work and home or when home or work dominates by choice. Spillover occurs when there is meddling of one sphere of life with another. Also, numerous outcomes of work-life balance include personal satisfaction and well-being at work, improved and sustained performance at work and home, good interpersonal relationship, an effective communication, impact on others at work, family and friends, commitment, and efficiency (Nkanata, 2021).

E. Empirical Review

Ajala and Osunrinde (2020) conducted the influence of employee assistance program on employees' performance in selected organisations in Ondo and Edo States. An Ex-post facto type of research design was adopted for the study while stratified random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and sixty (360) staff. The findings concluded that employee assistance program such as counseling program, stress management program, supervisory program and conflict management program have a positive influence on the performance of workers. Based on these findings, management are advised to provide employee assistance programs where this is absent there is need to introduce this assistance program to give the workers a befitting welfare as it has been proven to have a strong influence on the performance of workers.

Jun-bang, Yen-chen Hsu and Ching-wen (2020) evaluated the employee assistance programs (EAP) and its performance: a checklist developed from a large sample of public agencies. Drawing on the IPOO (input-process-output-outcome) performance evaluation model, we generate the scale dimensions and items through a multi-method data collection approach, including a literature review, panel discussion and a series of qualitative interviews with program practitioners. Then, by surveying EAP practitioners from 135 government units in Taiwan, we confirmed the reliability, content and predictive validity of the instrument which consists of 27 items. There are five phases in the instrument include resource allocation, management support, plan making, program introduction, and service provision.

Okemwa, Atambo and Muturi (2019) investigated the influence of employee assistance program on the commitment of nurses in public hospitals in Nigeria. The hypothesis employee assistance program does not have significant influence on the commitment of nurses in public hospitals in Nigeria. The simple random sampling was used to select 364 nurses while cross-sectional research design

was used. Semi-structured questionnaires were used to collect data and descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data gathered. The findings revealed that there is a weak positive correlation between the employee assistance program and the level of commitment of the nurses as indicated by a Pearson's correlation coefficient of 0.394 significant at a 5% level of significance. More so, adequacy of EAPs indicated that there is a positive linear relationship between employee assistance and commitment. Given that the employee assistance program in public hospitals is inadequate, the study recommended that the public hospital management team should enhance the employee assistance program in terms of adequacy to improve on the levels of commitment of nurses.

Nkanata (2021) investigated the influence of employee assistance program in public level five hospitals in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to establish the influence of childcare program, counseling program and wellness program on staff retention. The study adopted descriptive and correlation research designs. The study targeted 472 doctors, 3318 nurses and 449 clinical officers from the 11 available public level five hospitals in Nigeria. The study further used a proportionate stratified random sampling to select eight (8) public level five hospitals, and a total sample size of 40 doctors, 278 nurses, and 37 clinical officers. Simple random sampling was used to select the study participants in each stratum. Data was gathered using a semi-structured questionnaire. Data was analyzed using E-view package, with descriptive and inferential statistics being used to analyze the gathered data. The study concluded that the employee assistance program significantly influenced the health workers' decision to continue working in the same institution. Recommendation for the management is that the selected five public hospitals in Nigeria should invest in improving the employee assistance programs as a means to encourage their employees which will in turn lead to improved employee retention.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. The study area

Lagos State was selected for the study due to its status as the business hub and center of excellence for the Southwest State. It was also the previous capital city of Nigeria and is constantly bustling with human activity. Additionally, Lagos State is home to the greatest number of businesses of all sizes that are opening up every month and year. The choice of this study location was made because Warmco Nigeria, Plc is a foreign-owned company with a high likelihood of EAP experiences among its personnel. It is implied that employers care more about the health and well-being of their workers than their counterparts in other industrialized nations.

B. Study design

A descriptive survey design was used in the study to create a comprehensive understanding of the title. The study utilized a descriptive research approach to investigate the employee support program and its impact. As a result, the design made it easier to analyze respondents in their natural environment—the workplace. Additionally, the descriptive study approach assisted in characterizing the research participants' attitudes as they examined the employee support program concerning organizational performance.

C. Study population and sampling

Employees of Wamco Nigeria, Plc served as the research study's population framework. The firm's human resources department reports that 652 employees, including junior, senior, and management cadre members, are employed by the company. The 248 sample size was calculated using the Taro Yemane formula. The foreign-owned company was chosen because of its excellent organizational structure, lengthy history of operation, and comparatively higher workforce size.

D. Data collection instruments/techniques

Convenience sampling was the method employed for the sample. Data were collected from participants in every organizational cadre, which included management, senior, and junior employees. The Human Resource Department received the Google form questionnaire, and 200 respondents successfully filled it up.

E. Data analysis

Regression analysis, was obtained via the EVIEW statistics program and produced the t-statistics and Durbin Watson statistic, which was used to examine the data from the Google form questionnaire. The research's hypotheses were examined at a significance level of 5%.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The test statistical results for the first null hypothesis are shown in Table 1. The table shows that the organization's employee assistance program (EAP) had a positive regression coefficient of 0.439386, which increased effectiveness and efficiency by 44%. This demonstrated the favorable relationship between the effectiveness and efficiency of the employee support program. This suggested that the null hypothesis, according to which employee assistance programs have no appreciable impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of the company, ought to be disproved. Thus, an employee support program has a big impact on the efficacy and efficiency of the company. As a consequence, the coefficient of determination confirmed that the employee support program within the organization was responsible for 67.58% of the effectiveness and efficiency that the organization experienced. The variables have no serial auto-correlation, according to the Durbin-Watson statistics that were calculated.

Table 1: Test of Hypothesis one

Hypothesis One: Employee assistance program has no significant effect on effectiveness and efficiency of Wamco Nigeria Plc.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-calculated	P-value
C	-0.790244	0.259204	-3.048731	0.0026
Well program	0.439386	0.045922	9.568061	0.0000
Stress program	0.361755	0.083915	4.310998	0.0000
Social program	0.172547	0.055715	3.096936	0.0022
Mental health program	0.070341	0.056999	1.234062	0.2187
Family program	0.218456	0.049247	4.435945	0.0000
Counselling program	0.041208	0.045896	0.897853	0.3704
Health program	-0.083491	0.054649	-1.527766	0.1282
	OTHER STATISTICS	TEST	STATISTICS	
R-Squared	0.675886		Mean dependent var	2.5105000
Adjusted R-squared	0.662310		S.D. dependent var	1.200492
S.E. Regression	0.697619		Akaike info criterion	2.161668
Sum squared residual	92.95436		Schwarz criterion	2.310093
Log likelihood	-207.1668		Hannan-Quinn criteria	2.221733
F-statistics	49.78729		Durbin-Watson stat	2.054246
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source Research computation, 2023

Test are carried out at 5% level of significance

****AP= Available program**

The results of the investigation into the study's first hypothesis—that Wamco Nigeria Plc's organizational efficiency is influenced by its health care assistance program—are displayed in Table 1. The wellness program (t=9.568061, p>0.05), stress program (t=4.310998, p>0.05), social program (t=3.096936, p>0.05), and family program (t=4.435945, p>0.05) were identified from the table. This demonstrates the health, stress, social, and family programs that Wamco Nigeria, Plc employees have access to. The calculated value of p for the variable was below the 5% critical value. This demonstrated that the variables and organizational performance had a substantial link. Additionally, the mental health program (t=-1.527766, p<0.05), counseling program (t=0.897853, p<0.05), and mental health program (t=0.07341, p<0.05). The calculated value of p for the variable exceeded the critical value of 5%. This demonstrated that the factors and organizational

performance did not significantly correlate. Through an employee support program designed to increase the value of the individual on the job, the organization could improve performance. Additionally, the results of additional test statistics computed for hypothesis one demonstrated that having access to employee assistance will have a significant impact on organisational performance. Specifically, the coefficient of determination (R²) calculated at 0.68% indicated that a good employee assistance program contributed approximately 68% of organisational performance, as demonstrated by Wamco Nigeria Plc employees. Furthermore, the p-value of the F-statistics obtained for the test 0.0000 was less than the critical value of 5% with a significant F-statistical value of 49.78729. Lastly, the Durbin-Watson statistics calculated for the test, 2.054246, indicated a positive auto-correlation between the availability of EAP and organisational performance.

Table 2: Test of Hypothesis Two

Examine the Influence of Health Care Assistance Program and Organisational Efficiency and Effectiveness.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-calculated	P-value
C	1.814239	0.333891	5.433629	0.0000
Health 1	-0.018062	0.074947	0.240993	0.8098
Health 2	0.057336	0.085636	0.669532	0.5040
Health 3	0.061474	0.097183	0.632564	0.5278
Health 4	-0.181020	0.089692	-2.018235	0.0449
Health 5	0.163360	0.101366	1.611580	0.1087
	OTHER STATISTICS	Test	STATISTICS	
R-Squared	0.034573		Mean dependent var	2.105000
Adjusted R-squared	0.009691		S.D. dependent var	1.200492
S.E. Regression	1.194661		Akaike info criterion	3.223143
Sum squared residual	276.8797		Schwarz criterion	3.322092
Log likelihood	-316.3143		Hannan-Quinn criteria	3.263186
F-statistics	1.389465		Durbin-Watson stat	1.141473
Prob (F-statistic)	0.229851			

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2023 (E-view 12)

****Test are carried out at 5% level of significance**

Table 2 above presented the result of the test of hypothesis two. Observing the result on the table, it was discovered that p-value of the statistical computed for the variable of Health care and organisational performance was greater than the critical value of 5%. This shows that the null hypothesis which stated that health care has significant influence on organisational performance. From the table, it was discovered that Health care and organisational effectiveness and efficiency ($t=-2.018235$ $p>0.05$). The value of p computed for the variable was less than the critical value of 5%. This showed that there was significant relationship between variables and organisational effectiveness and efficiency. Moreover, health care and employee commitment ($t=0.240993$ $p<0.05$), Health care and organisational productivity ($t=0.669532$ $p<0.05$), Health care and good organisational performance ($t=0.632564$ $p<0.05$), Health care and employee teamwork ($t=1.611580$ $p<0.05$). The value of p computed for the variable was greater than the critical value of 5%. This showed that the variables have no significant relationship between variables and organisational performance.

The ability of the organisation to enhance their performance could be attained through Health care assistance program that aimed at increasing value of the employee on the job.

The result of other test statistics computed for the hypothesis two revealed that health care program will contribute significantly to organisational performance. The coefficient of determination (R^2) calculated of 0.035% showed that approximately 3.5% of organisational performance was as a result of good health care assistance program exhibited by employees of Wamco Nigeria, Plc. More so, the p-value of the F- statistics obtained for the test 0.0000 was less than critical value of 5% with significant F-statistical value of 1.389465. This indicated that null hypothesis two which stated that health care program do not significantly influence organisational performance in Wamco Nigeria Plc is rejected. The Durbin-Watson statistics calculated for the test is 1.141473 indicated that there is positive auto-correlation between health care program and organisational performance.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study extends the concept of employees' assistance program to workers in the private sector of Nigeria, under the general objective of the effects of employees' assistance program on organisational performance. The primary data was used; the data collected were analyzed using regression analysis derived from EViews statistics tool which generated the t-statistics and Durbin Watson statistics. The findings show that available employees' assistance program of Wamco Nigeria which include wellness program, stress management program, social program and family program can be of enormous help to improve and sustain performance of the organisation. Furthermore, the rate at which the employees are being effective and efficient could be determined by the level of the health care program available over a period of time.

Based on the findings, the roles that employee assistance program played in increasing the productivity, management should endeavor to improve and sustain the employee assistance program available to improve organisational performance. Management should also make it a priority to improve health care assistance program for the employees and make it available for both the new employee and the existing ones so as to improve overall performance of the organisation.

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